

Identifying Impact of Software Dependencies on Replicability of Biomedical Workflows

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Abstract

Complex data driven experiments form the basis of biomedical research. Recent findings warn that the context in which the software is run, that is the infrastructure and the third party dependencies, can have a crucial impact on the final results delivered by a computational experiment. This implies that in order to replicate the same result, not only the same data must be used, but also it must be run on an equivalent software stack.

In this paper we present the VFramework that enables assessing replicability of workflows. It identifies whether any differences in software dependencies among two executions of the same workflow exist and whether they have impact on the produced results. We also conduct a case study in which we investigate the impact of software dependencies on replicability of Taverna workflows used in biomedical research of Huntington's disease. We re-execute analysed workflows in environments differing in operating system distribution and configuration.

The results show that the VFramework can be used to identify the impact of software dependencies on the replicability of biomedical workflows. Furthermore, we observe that despite the fact that the workflows are executed in a controlled environment, they still depend on specific tools installed in the environment. The context model used by the VFramework improves the deficiencies of provenance traces and documents also such tools. Based on our findings we define guidelines for workflow owners that enable them to improve replicability of their workflows.

Keywords: reproducibility, verification, validation, workflow, context model

1. Introduction

Research performed in Bioinformatics requires special tooling, software and processes that allow researchers to link, transform, visualise and interpret the data [1], [2]. Data produced in such experiments is often reused to build new experiments [3]. However, the low maturity of tools and the possible lack of scientific scrupulousness [4] led to a low reproducibility and replicability of experiments in natural sciences in general [5], [6]. Many problems can be attributed to the fact that the software is not available any more [5]. This may appear to be a pure management issue that can be overcome by imposing better policies, but recent findings show that also the context in which the software is run, that is the infrastructure and the third party dependencies, can have a crucial impact on the final results delivered by a computational experiment. In [7] the authors demonstrate that a different version of the operating system used for neuroimaging analysis in clinical research produces different visualisations. This implies that in order to replicate the same result, not only the same data must be used, but also it must be run on an equivalent software stack.

Workflow engines were proposed to bring some standardisation, as well as to hide complexity of the underlying infrastructure. Workflow engines like VisTrails[8], Kepler [9] or Taverna [10] have become popular in research areas like Astronomy or Bioinformatics[11]. They enable researchers to graphically represent their experiments in form of workflows that can be built using pre-defined elements. These elements range from dedicated data parsers to interfaces for calling external web services. Workflows can also be shared with other researchers, so that they can replicate the original experiment or reuse it. Independent peers can verify the research by re-executing the workflow and establish trust that the data produced in the experiment is correct. This in turn accelerates research, because peers have higher confidence to reuse others workflows and data.

In spite of such a standardisation, a recent study [12] reports that only 30% of almost 1500 Taverna workflows published on myExperiment [13] can be re-executed. This does not imply that the execution produces correct results, but simply that the workflow executes. myExperiment does not provide any means to assess replicability of deposited workflows. So far there is no practice to provide data that would enable verification and validation of workflows re-executions. The provenance traces do not contain complete data describing workflow execution and there is no information on the environment in which the workflow was executed - provenance traces model relations between data and document values obtained during particular execution, but do not specify software and hardware used to process this data.

The problem thus remains on how to identify and store such data. Workflows share common infrastructure with other software running in the operating system and can delegate tasks specified in the workflow to be executed by tools installed in the environment. Such tools may require a specific configuration and presence of further tools that depend on specific software libraries or dedicated hardware. All these dependencies constitute a workflow execution context that needs to be captured, and verified and validated to state whether the workflow was replicable.

In this paper we investigate the impact of software dependencies on the replicability of biomedical workflows authored in Taverna. For that purpose we use the VFramework [14] that can verify and validate workflow re-executions. Thus, we can identify whether any differences in software dependencies among two executions of the same workflow exist and whether they have impact on the produced results. The VFramework uses the context model [15] to document environments in which the workflow executes and thus enables comparison of workflow executions without necessity of accessing both environments at the same time. By comparing context models of workflow executions we verify whether the workflow re-execution was obtained in a compliant way. The context model integrates ontologies that describe workflow and its environment. It includes not only high level description of workflow steps and services but also low level technical details on infrastructure, including hardware, software, and data. Furthermore, we use a set of automatically generated validation requirements and format-based metrics to check whether workflow re-executions produce the same results.

We conduct a case study in which we investigated the impact of software dependencies on replicability of Taverna workflows used in biomedical research for investigating the molecular mechanisms that are involved in Huntington's disease (HD). The selected workflows require multiple local dependencies ranging from additional libraries, scripts, and specific packages to external services for completing workflow steps. We investigate to what extent the impact of external services can be minimised by using service mock-ups. We also test in what way automatic workflow execution capturing helps in identifying reasons for workflows to break. We test the impact of software dependencies by re-executing the workflows not only in exact environments, but also in similar environments, that is, differing in operating system distribution and configuration. The workflows consist of steps that are representative for the majority of Taverna workflows published on myExperiment [12]. Despite the fact, that our discussion is focused on Taverna

workflows, the challenges and ways of addressing them remain valid for other workflow systems as well, differing in the actual technical implementation.

The paper is structured as follows. In Section 2 we present related work on workflow management systems, provide an overview of reproducibility and replicability challenges, and discuss the context of scientific experiment including means of its capturing and storing. Section 3 provides an overview of the VFramework. Section 4 describes steps of the VFramework that capture the original workflow execution, while Section 5 describes the steps that verify and validate the workflow re-execution. In Section 6 we present a case study from the biomedical research domain in which we applied the VFramework to identify the impact of software dependencies on the reproducibility of workflows. In Section 7 we provide the discussion of the results and provide recommendations. Conclusions are in Section 8.

2. Related work

In the following section we describe examples of related work. We first discuss different workflow management systems and then we provide an overview of studies related to replicability of computational studies that emphasise the necessity to document the workflow execution context and show that no sufficient verification and validation method is in use. Finally, we review in what way the software execution context can be modelled and automatically captured.

2.1. Workflow management systems

Workflow engines like VisTrails[8], Kepler [9] or Taverna [10] have become popular in research areas like astronomy or bioinformatics. They enable researchers to graphically represent their experiments in form of workflows that can be built using pre-defined elements. These elements range from dedicated data parsers to interfaces for calling external web services. A comparison of workflow management systems is presented in [16]. The authors compared Taverna, Kepler and Activiti [17]. The first two are typically used in scientific settings, while Activiti is used in business settings, because it allows modelling of workflows using the Business Process Modelling Notation (BPMN). The results of the comparison are summarized in Table 1. The compared systems were implemented in Java and each of them supports scripting languages. Taverna allows Beanshells that are based on Java, Kepler allows for Python scripts, while Activiti supports a wide range of different scripting languages. Each of the workflow systems records the workflow provenance in a database. The traces contain information specifying who ran the experiment at what point in time, what data was provided as input and what intermediate data was exchanged between the workflow steps.

Due to the similarities among workflow engines, we chose one workflow system on which we applied the VFramework for verification and validation of workflow re-executions. For this reason the discussion presented in this dissertation is focused on Taverna workflows, but the challenges and ways of addressing them remain valid for other workflow systems as well, differing only in the actual technical implementation. We also applied the VFramework to experiments in other technical settings. These workflows did not require workflow engines because they were modelled as bash scripts or python scripts, still working successfully. However, these examples are beyond the scope of this paper.

2.2. Reproducibility and Replicability challenges

Table 1: Features of workflow systems [16].

Engine	Implement.	Script Language Support	Designer Support	Execution Engine	Provenance
Taverna	Java	Beanshell	Standalone	Integrated with designer	Database (Apache Derby)
Kepler	Java	Python	Standalone	Integrated with designer	Database (HSQLDB)
Actiivti	Java	JavaScript, Python, Ruby, etc.	Eclipse IDE	Web application or Java program	Database (H2 DB)

The RDA working group on dynamic data citation¹ produced recommendations [18] on how to deal with changing datasets. One of the recommendations says that the data must be timestamped and all insert and delete actions must be marked so that the state of the database at the moment when the experiment was conducted could be restored. Otherwise running the same workflow with different input data means running a different experiment. The replicability [19] of research assumes, that we can obtain the same results in the same conditions, in our case that we can obtain the same result using the same inputs and identical/compatible environment. Reproducibility can be understood as obtaining the similar results in a different experiment. This could mean using different sample data, different infrastructure or even a different workflow.

The study presented in [7] revealed the impact of a system and software version on the final results. Analysis performed using the *FreeSurfer* software package did not break, but lead to different results depending on the operating system and libraries, and made previous analysis performed on a different environment not comparable. The authors encourage to "provide not only the version of FreeSurfer that was used but also details on the operating system version and workstation" as it affected the results obtained. While the example above uses a customised software, rather than workflows, similar analyses are performed via workflows, for example the analysis of kidney biopsy microscopy images using Taverna in [20].

Reasons for Taverna workflows to break were described in [21]. The authors show examples in which a workflow that was re-executable was in fact delivering altered results due to the changes in the third party resource. The authors claim that publishing requirements for software libraries used by the workflow and sample output data could decrease the decay of workflows.

A recent study [12] reports that only 30% of almost 1500 Taverna workflows published on myExperiment can be re-executed. This does not imply that the execution produces correct results, but simply that the workflow executes. So far there is no practice at all to provide data that would enable verification and validation of workflow re-executions. Research Objects [22] are aggregations of resources used in scientific investigations that enhance the description of experiments, but they have certain limitations due to their focus on the scientific aspect of the experiment and not on the technical details of its implementation. Thus, the problem remains on how to identify and store such data.

¹<https://rd-alliance.org/groups/data-citation-wg.html>

2.3. Software execution context

The execution context of a scientific workflow consists of software and hardware needed for its execution. These software and hardware can also be referred to as dependencies.

Sumatra is a system capable of capturing execution context [23]. The context consists, among others, of: python libraries used by the process, basic information about the platform like CPU type, IP address and the operating system version. The authors motivate the necessity of recording which files were accessed during execution of scripts, and which source code version was used to perform the experiment with the fact that the researchers are very often not aware of the system configuration and software versions when performing their computations.

We use the *context model*, described in [15], to store descriptive meta-data and documentation of the workflow and its environment. It is a meta-model designed according to the principle of modularity. The architecture is centred on a core model that is extended by models, depending on the requirements of the application domain. The meta-model is implemented as an OWL ontology. The ontology mapping allows for a realisation of the model integration. This architecture is depicted in Figure 1.

The core model is based on the ArchiMate enterprise modelling language [24]. It includes concepts on business and technical layers ranging from services, process steps, and data exchanged between the steps, down to the technical infrastructure, including hardware, software, and files. An example extension is the ontology on software dependencies based on CUDF (Common Upgradeability Description Format) [25], which provides detailed modelling support for various relations, such as dependencies or conflicts between packages. In this paper we refer to the above described structure as context meta model, while to the instances of it as context model.

The context model that we use in the VFramework was developed in parallel to the PROV-O [26] and has a broader focus, due to its different original application domain - business process preservation. The context model aims to describe the whole context of a workflow execution - classical provenance is only a part that describes actual data produced during a concrete execution of the workflow. The core concepts of the PROV-O model are: Agent, Entity, and Activity. These concepts would correspond to the business layer of the context model. The extensions of the PROV model, such like PROV-DM, add more information on the data model introducing concepts that specify relations between data items (e.g was derived from, was associated with). However, there is currently no extension to describe dependencies, like the CUDF does for describing Debian packages. Hence, the whole PROV family can be seen as a compatible model to the context model that models provenance information of a data record, but not as a standalone model which describes also the details of the software and hardware dependencies that were involved in producing the data. In other words, the PROV approach is more data focused, while the context model is more process focused - it documents both the data (provenance) but also the way in which the data was processed (dependencies).

CDE [27] is a tool for packaging completed environments into virtual machines. It requires users to prepend CDE commands to scripts or binaries. CDE intercepts system calls and gathers all files and binaries that were used in the execution. However, CDE is not capable of detecting external calls, for example to web services used in the workflow. Also local service applications that run in the background and are initiated before the workflow execution are not detected.

The process migration framework (PMF) [28] does not have these limitations and is capable of extracting a process from a Debian GNU/Linux based operating systems in which the process shares resources with other processes. The PMF saves the results into the context model [15]. PMF is based on the Linux tool `strace`², which logs all calls between

²<http://sourceforge.net/projects/strace/>

Figure 1: Overview of the context model: core ontology and extensions [15]

a software program and the system. It records which programs (operating system processes) were called, what files were accessed or created, and which connections to other services were opened, for example connections to a local database or a remote web service. This data contains the exact commands and their parameters, as well concrete addresses of services. Furthermore, it identifies which of the identified files are a part of the default operating system software sources, so-called Debian packages, and groups these together. This leads to a concise and semantically richer description of the actual dependencies of the workflow - instead of a flat list of potentially thousands of files, one obtains a much shorter list of packages. When the PMF is run in the original environment to create the context model it downloads packages that were identified in the system, as well as extracts files from the original system that were used for processing. Using this data and Vagrant³ it can create a new virtual machine that is configured in the same way as the original one was. In Section 3 we describe how we use the PMF for the dynamic analysis of workflow execution and later its verification.

3. VFramework

A first conceptual design of the VFramework was outlined in [14]. Via a number of conceptual and, finally, fully implemented pilots the framework has been concretized, defining the individual steps and the data collected at each of them in detail. The resulting framework presented in this paper provides a comprehensive view on the data required to validate and verify the correctness of a process re-execution as well as a precise process of how to collect it. In the remainder of this section we provide an overview of the framework structure and explain in which settings the framework can be used. We describe the particular steps of the VFramework in Sections 4 and 5.

The design goals for the VFramework go beyond the mere re-execution within relatively short time frames, but include digital preservation settings in which workflows potentially need to be re-executed at much later points in time in different computational environments, when the original workflow may not be executable any more. These long-term considerations, however, turn out to be essential even in short-term re-execution settings due to the rapid change of the underlying technology at the hardware and software level.

³<https://docs.vagrantup.com/v2/boxes.html>

Figure 2: Framework for verification and validation of re-executed workflows.

A workflow running in the original environment can be extracted and moved either to a new environment or preserved in a repository. Such a new environment is often referred to as the redeployment environment. In many cases the original system may not exist anymore. Therefore, we have to ensure that contemporary access to both the original and a new execution environment is not necessary, as this is not feasible in re-execution settings. The preferred way to compare these two executions is to collect data from the original environment and to use it as a reference in the environment in which the workflow is re-executed.

These requirements are reflected by the VFramework which is depicted in Figure 2. It consists of two sequences of actions. The first one collects information about the original execution of the workflow in the original environment. The second one uses this information to verify and validate the re-execution of the workflow in the redeployment environment. The context model [15] stores information collected in the first and provides this information in the second phase. The first three steps of the framework, which are performed in the original environment, are gradually adding information to the context model. Later this information is processed using tools to verify and validate the workflow re-execution.

4. Describing original environment

Scientific workflows can require workflow management systems for execution. Besides these, workflows can also be implemented as scripts using various programming languages, or can be verbally defined in text documents and later executed manually. To verify and validate each workflow type, one can develop methods and tools specific to a particular workflow implementation. Development of methods and tools for each workflow type would result in duplication of efforts and multiplicity of similar but not compatible tools. This is due to the similarities between the workflow systems and the fact that all of the workflows are finally executed by an operating system that transforms them into system processes.

Hence, a better approach is to provide a common way for verification and validation of workflows. This can be achieved by transforming workflow specifications into a common model which analysis can be performed in the same way regardless of the original workflow specification. The common model is an abstraction of the original workflow model that contains information needed for verification and validation of workflows' execution. The process of abstracting workflow specifications requires identification of mappings between the concepts and development of

tools that convert workflow specifications into the common model. The mappings specify, for example, that each *port* in Taverna is a *Data Object* in ArchiMate, or that each *processor* is a *Business Process*. The specification of a mapping is a model engineering task and requires a good understanding of both models. This can be a complex task, because not always one to one mapping of concepts can be found. In such situations a combination of concepts from one model may be used to express similar information about a single concept in the other model. However, the definition of a mapping is done once only and later can be applied to all workflows for which the mapping was defined. In our analysis we show how Taverna workflows are transformed into the context model that is a common model that can be used to model various types of workflows.

In the remainder of this section we describe in detail the *Run static analysis* and the *Run dynamic analysis* steps of the VFramework. By performing these steps we describe workflow structure and identify its dependencies. We also present the *Define validation metrics* step in which we generate validation requirements used to validate the re-execution.

4.1. Run static analysis

Workflows can be executed within a dedicated workflow engine, but even this does not imply that workflows are separated from the environment in which the workflow engine runs. In fact workflows can have interactions with other software that is running on the same system, for example, by connecting to a database server. Therefore, often before the workflow is started, the other services must be enabled, or they are started during workflow execution. All these additional services, on which the workflow depends, belong to the workflow's context and must be captured in the original environment.

Knowing this context we can define workflow boundaries that specify which of the identified dependencies are integral part of the workflow, that is, which of them are within the workflow boundary. Such dependencies must be verified and validated to confirm workflow replicability. The dependencies that lay outside of the workflow boundary, so called external dependencies, are also needed for the workflow to execute, however, they are not an integral part of the workflow. Furthermore, they are often provided by third parties. For this reason the analysis can be limited due to a lack of access and we can only check whether they are accessible and interact in the same way with the workflow. For example, to reproduce the result of a workflow execution that uses a web service provided by a third party to fetch data, it is essential that the web service is available in an unchanged form. If we switch to any other compatible web service, the workflow performance is not affected, because the service provides only data and does not implement any processing logic. For this reason, it is an external dependency which availability and conformance must be checked, but there is no need (and no means) to verify and validate it. Hence the analysis of workflow context allows us to identify which dependencies must be present during the workflow execution and for which of them we must collect data that enables their verification and validation.

We use the context model to describe the workflow and its environment. We perform a static analysis using the workflow definition file. We use the Taverna2Archi⁴ and the Archi2OWL⁵ converters to automatically convert the specification of a workflow into the core ontology of the context model. The first tool reads the Taverna workflow definition file and generates the core of the context model using pre-defined modelling patterns, while the second one transforms the model into an OWL ontology. For other than Taverna workflows this is done manually using Archi⁶

⁴<http://www.ifs.tuwien.ac.at/dp/process/projects/tavernaExtractor.html>

⁵<http://www.ifs.tuwien.ac.at/dp/process/projects/archi2OWL.html>

⁶<http://www.archimatetool.com>

modelling tool, or directly in an ontology editor, for example, Protege⁷.

The benefit of using the ontology representation of the presented model is the possibility of querying the model. Thus without manually working with the model we can:

- Identify whether the workflow has external dependencies, like for example web services.
- Check if any Beanshell scripts declare usage of external Java libraries.
- List workflow steps, as well as their inputs and outputs.

We use this information in the next step to configure the environment in which the workflow executes.

4.2. *Run dynamic analysis*

Figure 3 depicts the *Run dynamic analysis* step of the VFramework in detail. In this step we first select the test data to be used during the dynamic analysis of the workflow execution and show how this kind of analysis identifies local dependencies of the workflow that lay within the workflow boundaries. Then we show how to deal with external dependencies that are services running in parallel, which only exchange data with the workflow, and are outside of the workflow boundaries. Last but not least, we capture provenance data of a workflow execution.

The outcomes of this step are:

- Workflow context model extended with information on infrastructure components needed to execute the workflow and also with file formats of each workflow output
- Dependency report summarizing workflow dependencies in a human readable form
- Dump of intercepted communication between the workflow and external services
- Provenance traces holding the actual values of executed workflow instances
- Copy of data files accessed by the workflow during execution

4.2.1. *Local dependencies*

Local dependencies of the workflow are all system components used during workflow execution that are within the workflow boundary, which was defined in the previous step. Examples range from software libraries imported by scripts, and shell tools invoked from the workflow, to research area specific software tools. Also the specific version of the workflow engine, as well as the version of the operating system is important. In case of package based systems like Linux the exact version of packages installed must be documented.

Due to the amount and the granularity of information needed, the manual description of local dependencies is limited. An alternative approach is the virtualisation of the complete environment in which the workflow executes. The amount of data that is captured is significantly higher than the size of the workflow. Furthermore, this approach does not provide any documentation of workflow dependencies and simply hides the complexity of dependencies inside the virtual machine. Therefore, the preferred approach is to document the workflow using an automatically created workflow model that is created by monitoring workflow execution. Such a model can be used to re-create the workflow environment in a new system, because it contains technical dependencies required directly or indirectly by

⁷<http://protege.stanford.edu>

Figure 3: The *Run dynamic analysis* step of the VFramework in detail.

the workflow [29]. Furthermore such a model contains explicit documentation of workflow dependencies and without re-executing the workflow we can analyse the dependencies and identify workflow requirements to configure the new environment appropriately. For this reason, we use the PMF (see Section 2.3) to monitor an execution of a workflow and to create its context model.

We use the context model to generate a dependency report that provides a concise overview of workflow specific dependencies. The tool for dependency report generation uses five predefined SPARQL queries to process the data from the context model (after noise reduction). The report summarizes five main aspects of the workflow execution that must be verified:

- **Shell calls** When a workflow uses any tool that is installed in a system, it makes a shell call. The report lists all

commands that were executed and provides a list of Debian packages and files that are used during the call.

- **Remote services** If a workflow uses an external service, then the exact address of the service is provided.
- **Specific file dependencies** These are all files that are used by a workflow but cannot be attributed to any of the installed packages. Usually, these are all sorts of configuration files and additional libraries that might have been installed manually in the system.
- **Data files processed by the workflow** These are all data files that were either input files of the workflow or were created during workflow execution, for example, temporary files, logs, or workflow outputs.
- **Specific Debian packages** The list contains all Debian packages that must be installed in the system, when executing the workflow. The packages are a superset of packages identified for each shell call.

The dependency report is easy to be read by a human, but presents only a limited view on the workflow context. The report is useful when installing the workflow in a new environment to get an overview of interactions the workflow has. However, for the verification we use the complete context model which includes the workflow engine dependencies.

4.2.2. *External dependencies*

The external dependencies of a workflow are all kinds of services that are used to perform workflow steps but are not under direct control of the workflow engine. These can be services that were started in parallel on a local machine or services that are hosted on a different platform than the one executing the workflow. The workflow only exchanges data with them. Web services are an example of external dependencies and according to [12] they are the most common external dependency of Taverna workflows.

When a workflow is re-executed in a new environment, it may happen that a third party web service is not available any more, or it was upgraded to a newer version that delivers altered results due to a different computational algorithm. In such cases, the workflow may either break or can produce altered results. The possible solutions to circumvent this problem are:

- To use a different service that is compliant with the original one.
- To create a mock-up of the service that can provide correct responses for the requests recorded in the original environment.

A mock-up simulates the original web service. The most basic form of a mock-up implements a lookup table. Such a mock-up is able to send back responses to requests which were previously recorded in the original environment. As a consequence only messages which were intercepted can be replayed. The solution does not have any computing capabilities as the original system may have. However, in many cases the information collected may be sufficient to meet legal requirements or compliance regulations for documenting and proofing the correctness of workflow execution.

A mock-up can also be used as a model to validate the identity of a proposed substitute web service. The requests stored by the mock-up can be used to query the substitute, and responses received can be compared against responses of the mock-up. This approach increases the likelihood of matching a correct substitute in comparison to relying on the web service description only. A similar concept which uses provenance data to find substitutes for missing tasks in scientific workflows is described in [30].

Independent of the chosen solution, we need to collect the evidence to which we can refer when either assessing compliance of a substitute service, or when creating a mock-up. In [31] we described the Web Service Monitoring Framework that describes how to collect such evidence. In [32] we described ways of creating mock-ups.

4.2.3. Provenance data

Workflows differ in the way they produce data. This depends on their implementation. Some of the workflows process data inside the system memory and in the final step write data to the hard disk. Some other save also intermediate results to the disk and thus enable tracing workflow execution and validation of intermediate data. There are also workflows that write the result to the standard output and create no files. Various tools can be used to collect the data either from the disk, system memory or from specific system interfaces, like for example network interfaces. The problem of capturing workflow instance data was recognized by the workflow community and addressed by integration of provenance collection mechanisms that are built-in mechanisms of workflow management systems. They enable automatic capturing of data produced during execution.

For the current implementation we used Janus, the provenance representation natively supported by Taverna. However, Janus can be replaced by any other provenance ontology like PROV due to the modularity of the context model. We capture provenance by running Taverna in a mode that saves provenance data of a workflow execution. Taverna stores the input and output data of each workflow step in a local database. We use the Provenance Extractor⁸ to extract this data and export it in the Janus ontology format.

We also use the provenance traces to enrich the context model with information on the data format of each of the outputs of the workflow steps. As explained in the next section, this information facilitates the validation process by allowing choosing a correct data comparison tool. We obtain this information by running the DROID⁹ characterisation tool that performs automated identification of file formats. We use the PREMIS ontology [33], which is an international metadata standard widely used in the digital curation domain, to store the format information and to extend the context model.

4.3. Define validation metrics

To define a universal set of requirements we performed top-down and bottom-up analyses. In the top-down analysis we focused on the scientific method. One of its main principles is that the scientific experiment must be repeatable [34]. We also analysed Taverna documentation and identified that the finest granularity of available data that can be captured in the workflow system is a single workflow step. Based on this analysis we formulated the following requirement: "The results of each workflow step must be the same".

We also performed a bottom-up analysis by investigating 7 workflows from 4 different domains. For each of the workflows we brainstormed to define requirements that validate whether the workflow re-execution was identical (or similar within an acceptable range) with the original one. To measure the similarity of workflow executions we defined metrics that we derived from measurements taken during both executions. We took into account the available provenance data to identify which data is available and can be used to calculate these metrics.

The analysis of defined requirements revealed that all functional requirements deal with the correctness of a single workflow step execution and the best way to validate it was to check each of its output ports. There was only one non-functional requirement that the computation time shall be similar.

⁸<http://www.ifs.tuwien.ac.at/dp/process/projects/provenanceExtractor.html>

⁹<http://sourceforge.net/projects/droid/>

Furthermore, we noticed that the comparison of data must take into account the format of the data and therefore must be made using appropriate tools. For example if two PNG images depicting the same phenomenon are compared by computing a hash value, they can be detected as being different due to different metadata descriptions. A correct way to perform this comparison is to compare the features of the images using software for image analysis. In case of textual data formats using the right comparator also has an influence on the validation result. For example, two XML documents having different ordering of elements, but otherwise containing the same data, using a simple text comparison would detect discrepancies, while a dedicated XML comparator ignores the ordering and thus confirms the equivalence.

Based on the top-down and the bottom-up analyses of workflows, we conclude that:

- For each workflow step we can generate a functional requirement which states that the results produced by the workflow step must be the same.
- For each workflow step we can generate a non-functional requirement which states that the step execution duration shall be similar.
- Each functional requirement can be evaluated by calculating metrics for each of the outputs of the corresponding workflow step.
- The data must be compared taking into account the format of the data.

We use metrics to quantify the distance between two workflow executions using measures derived from captured data for each execution. For example, we use the absolute error count of the number of different pixels for each channel to measure how far two PNG images differ.

However, apart from the metric, we must provide its target value to indicate which metric value fulfils the requirement. Furthermore, if we allow alterations in the workflow execution, for example rounding errors when comparing two floating point numbers, then we need to specify a tolerance on metric target value that fulfils the requirement.

Based on these conclusions we automatically generate requirements, metrics and their target values. The generated requirements validate whether the workflow re-execution is identical. We document the validation requirements using the VPlan [35] ontology.

4.4. Summary

The context model which was gradually extended during the application of the VFramework in the original environment is schematically depicted in Figure 4. It depicts individuals generated for a single workflow step *Visualise Temperature* that has one input and one output. For the readability purposes we present an excerpt of the model. Further examples can be found in Section 6 or downloaded from here¹⁰. In the figure different background colour of elements depicts different modules (ontologies) of the context model. There are five parts that were created during the VFramework application:

- *workflow model core* (yellow) - the central element that describes the workflow model and is a basis for further extensions (see Section 4.1),
- *workflow dependencies* (green) - description of software and hardware components used by the workflow (see Section 4.2.1),

¹⁰<https://zenodo.org/record/47252>

Figure 4: Overview of the context model parts instantiated during the VFramework application: *workflow model core* (yellow), *workflow dependencies* (green), *workflow instance data* (dark grey), *file format specification* (orange), *validation requirements* (light grey).

- *workflow instance data* (dark grey) - data used, processed and produced by the workflow during its execution (see Section 4.2.3),
- *file format specification* (orange) - identified file format for the workflow instance data (see Section 4.2.3),
- *validation requirements* (light grey) - requirements and metrics used to validate the re-execution (see Section 4.3).

5. Verification and validation of workflow re-execution

In this section we describe the VFramework steps that are performed when the workflow is re-executed in a new environment. To complete them we collect information about the re-execution from the new environment and compare it to the information collected in the original environment, which was stored in the context model.

5.1. Verify environment

This is the first step performed in the environment in which the workflow is re-executed. The verification process is iterative and coupled with the validation process that is described in Section 5.2.

Figure 5 presents an overview of the verification and validation processes. We start by copying the workflow to a new environment in which the experiment is replicated. We run the workflow and monitor its execution using the PMF to create the context model of the re-executed workflow. We compare it to the original workflow model to verify

Figure 5: Verification of workflow re-execution as an iterative process.

whether the same dependencies were used to compute the result. If the workflow is executed in an environment configured in the exactly same way, then there are no differences between the context models. However, researchers can also replicate the workflow executions in already existing environments in which they used to run other workflows. Then there can be differences between the models, but they can have no impact on the result of the computation. To find out whether the differences between environments have impact on the workflow re-execution, we validate the re-execution in the *Validate workflow* step of the VFramework. When the validation is positive, that is the workflow re-execution matches the original execution, then such deviations are acceptable. Otherwise, the workflow environment has to be reconfigured so that the differences are eliminated. This process is iterative and repeated until the re-execution is valid or no differences between configurations of both environments exist. If the environment configurations are identical and the validation still fails, then this implies that the workflow re-execution is not replicable and may indicate that the original data was fabricated.

5.2. Validate workflow

We validate workflow re-execution by checking whether all metrics for the requirements defined in the step *Define validation metrics* are fulfilled. We compare the data and on that basis calculate the metrics' values using the captured data of the re-executed and the original workflow.

We automated the *Validate workflow* step by implementing the VPlanComparator. The VPlanComparator uses the context model to source the information on requirements, metrics and their target values, and location of data used for metric computation. The context model contains links to the actual data files that were captured in the original environment. The captured data consists of provenance traces and data files identified by the PMF in the *Run dynamic analysis* step of the VFramework.

We explained in Section 4.3 the impact of the data formats on the provenance data comparison process. The VPlanComparator uses a suitable comparator depending on the type of metric defined in the VPlan. We implemented seven comparators that allow computation of metrics for the following file formats: HTML, PDF, PNG, TEX, XML, and ZIP. If there is no suitable comparator for the identified format, then MD5 hashes are computed. The architecture of the VPlanComparator allows adding further comparators via a plugin mechanism.

Evaluation result: There are 2 not fulfilled metrics. Please see tables below for details.

Comparison performed using following workflow execution traces

Original Workflow

ID: 37b4d2fb-e71c-4b67-b7b3-17888ee82977

Timestamp: 2015-10-14 18:58:06.475

Compared Workflow

ID: ede04b87-5f58-4a89-b0c3-e179957cbad0

Timestamp: 2015-11-13 13:59:56.443

Table 1: Overview of requirements

Requirement	Description	Is Fulfilled
R1	The inputs to the workflow are the same	true
R2	The outputs of the workflow are the same	false
R3	The workflow step ExtractTemperature must have identical outputs	true
R4	The workflow step GetWeatherData must have identical outputs	true
R5	The workflow step MakeDecision must have identical outputs	true
R6	The workflow step ExtractWeatherType must have identical outputs	true
R7	The workflow step VisualiseTemperature must have identical outputs	false
R8	Execution duration of each of the workflow steps shall be similar	true

Table 2: List of requirements and metrics that failed.

Req	Sub-req	Sub-requirement description	Measurement point	Metric	Validity
R2	R7.1	The output plot of workflow step VisualiseTemperature must be identical	plot	ImageFingerPrintEquality	false
				ImageResolutionEquality	true
				AbsoluteErrorCount	false
R7	R7.1	The output plot of workflow step VisualiseTemperature must be identical	plot	ImageFingerPrintEquality	false
				ImageResolutionEquality	true
				AbsoluteErrorCount	false

Figure 6: Excerpt of a validation report

The VPlanComparator takes also into account that the sequence in which particular workflow steps are completed may sometimes differ and this has impact on the structure of provenance traces. This is because workflow engines are often multi-thread programs. For example, the Taverna workflow engine has a queue to which threads are submitted for execution [10]. If a list of values is passed to the workflow step for processing, then for each element a new thread is created and submitted to the queue. The processing of a next step begins when all of the threads belonging to a given step have finished their execution. Such a design makes it possible to process several steps at the same time. If many steps process lists of elements, there is a higher likelihood that the threads are ordered differently in the queue. This has no impact on the final result of the workflow run and the validity of results, but it results in different ordering of data captured for each step. Hence, the comparison process using provenance traces is not only comparison for equal text contents.

The VPlanComparator creates reports summarizing the validation results. The overall result of validation is pre-

sented and violated requirements and metrics are provided, if detected. Furthermore, detailed descriptions of metrics, their assignment to requirements, as well data formats identified are listed. Figure 6 presents an excerpt of a validation report. We can see that two requirements R2 & R7 are not fulfilled. This is because sub-requirement R7.1 is not fulfilled due to metrics *Image Fingerprint Equality* and *Absolute Error Count* being failing. The third metric *Image Resolution Equality* was fulfilled which implies that the workflow re-execution produced an image, but its contents differed.

6. Case study

In this case study we use three workflows that were designed for the research of Huntington's Disease (HD) by a group of scientists in the Human Genetics department of the Leiden University Medical Centre. We use these workflows as a representative example to evaluate the VFramework and to investigate replicability problems of workflows in the biomedical domain.

Huntington's Disease is one of the most commonly inherited neurodegenerative disorder in Europe, that affects 1 - 10/100.000 people [36]. HD is caused by a mutation in the huntingtin gene, a CAG expansion. This translates to a mutated protein with an expanded polyglutamine tract. Although the genetic mutation was identified 20 years ago [37], we still lack a cure or an effective treatment for HD. In addition, despite the extensive research in the field the mechanisms leading to the HD are still poorly understood.

Transcriptional deregulation is a prominent feature of HD with gene expression changes taking place even before first symptoms arise. Evidence points to changes in epigenetic mechanisms that may be responsible for such transcriptional abnormalities [38]. In this experiment the researchers investigated if epigenetics are involved in HD. Linking changes that occur in gene expression to epigenetic information might shed light on the disease aetiology.

For this they used publicly available datasets from HD gene expression data (from three different brain regions) [39] and data from the the ENCODE consortium describing information about the state of chromatin across the genome. These states were: active transcription start site (TSS) proximal promoter (TssA), bivalent regulatory region (TssBiv), heterochromatin (Het), and repressed Polycomb (ReprPC) [40]. They tested for overlaps between the two datasets (gene expression and epigenetic information) in order to identify chromatin states that are overrepresented among the differentially expressed genes and thus, further investigate whether the gene expression changes are linked to alterations in chromatin state. As a final step for their experiment, they modelled their results (genes overlapping with a particular chromatin state and genes differentially expressed in HD) into machine readable language using the nanopublication¹¹ schema [41].

To perform the experiment they implemented workflows in the Taverna workflow management system [42]. These workflows use the Rshell service for performing the data analysis in order to identify genes that overlap with a particular chromatin state, and a series of in house web services (Concept Profile Analysis [43][44]) that use literature information to annotate the lists of genes with the most representative biological processes. They also execute Ruby scripts to create the nanopublications.

These workflows are published in the *myExperiment*¹² - a social web platform for exchange of scientific workflows. They resemble characteristics of typical Taverna workflows. According to the study presented in [12] almost 30% of all Taverna workflows published on myExperiment use WSDL web services to perform tasks and 15% have local

¹¹<http://www.nanopub.org>

¹²<http://www.myexperiment.org>

tool invocations. Furthermore, almost 50% of all workflows use Beanshells that allow users to write their own code in a lightweight Java-like scripting language. Beanshells can import external Java libraries and therefore add further dependencies to the workflow. The local tool invocations may also be made by the Beanshells and may require particular software tools to be installed in the environment. The study shows that only 30% of workflows can be re-executed. In our case study we check what is the impact of workflow dependencies on its replicability and demonstrate how the VFramework verifies and validates the re-executions.

In Section 6.1 we present redeployment of the workflow in an equivalent Linux environment and show how to detect and aggregate specific workflow dependencies. The workflow uses WSDL web services to perform tasks. We compare two redeployments of this workflow, first using the original web service, second using a mock-up of the web service. We evaluate whether the mock-up has impact on the processing of the workflow and its results.

In Section 6.2 we present how to evaluate the impact of software dependencies of a workflow that uses an external service which is an R server running in parallel to the workflow engine. We show how the static analysis of the context model helps in identifying service dependencies. Furthermore, we check to what extent we can verify and validate tasks that are completed outside of the workflow engine, namely in the R server.

In Section 6.3 we apply the VFramework to a workflow that uses Ruby scripts to complete tasks. We investigate whether we can detect Ruby dependencies and thus verify the workflow execution. We also show that the provenance data can be incomplete when a workflow completes tasks using shell calls. In such cases we use files that were detected by the PMF to validate workflow re-execution.

The data used in the evaluation is available online¹³.

6.1. Annotate genes workflow

We first present the use case description and then describe how we completed the steps of the VFramework in the original and the redeployment environment.

6.1.1. Use case description

Figure 7 depicts the *annotate workflow*¹⁴ that is used to annotate gene lists with predefined concept sets such as biological processes or molecular functions. The workflow uses a local knowledge base to annotate a set of input genes. Therefore, this workflow takes as an input a list of comma separated *entrez gene identifiers*, the database name that will be used to map the gene ids to the local concept profile identifiers (in our case EG for Entrez gene identifiers), a cut-off parameter for the number of annotations to be obtained, and an identifier for the predefined concept set id that is used in the local database (for example 5 for biological processes or 3 for molecular function). The workflow uses *anni* web services. The web services of the workflow are described in more detail in [45].

6.1.2. Original environment

In the *Run static analysis* step of the VFramework we identify that:

- The workflow uses one WSDL web service hosted on a remote server.
- The workflow uses Beanshell scripts that do not require any additional libraries to be shipped with the workflow.
- The workflow uses XPath services.

¹³<https://zenodo.org/record/47252>

¹⁴<http://www.myexperiment.org/workflows/3921.html>

Figure 7: The *annotate* workflow.

Based on these results, in the *Run dynamic analysis* step of the VFramework we capture the communication between the workflow and the web service. The workflow owner confirmed that the web service is deterministic and hence there is no need for its continuous monitoring. We transform the captured data by grouping it into request and response pairs. We use this data to create a mock-up of the service when the workflow is re-executed.

We also monitor the workflow execution using the PMF. Figure 8a depicts the workflow context model created by the PMF. We can read from it:

- The unique identifier of the platform for which the capturing took place (*Node*).
- The name of the user who ran the workflow (*User*).
- The version of Taverna that was used for running the workflow (*System Software*).
- The IP Address, as well as the domain name of the WSDL web service (*Service, SOAP Service Interface, HTTP Service Interface*).

- The version of the operating system (*Operating System*).
- The workflow does not access files that are not included in the provenance traces (*Data File*).

There are also almost a thousand of *Data Files* that include specific Taverna dependencies and temporary files. To filter out only the workflow specific dependencies and thus increase the readability of the dependency report we use the calibration workflow that does no processing. We also monitor its execution with the PMF and then compare the context models of both workflows. The results of comparison are depicted in Figure 8b and Figure 8c.

Figure 8b depicts the elements that were not used by the calibration workflow and thus are specific to the analysed workflow. We can see that the number of *Data Files* was reduced from 964 to 12. The list contains nine files that are workflow data files such as input and output data. The other three files belong to the *java-7-oracle* installation and were not assigned to a corresponding *oracle-java-7-installer* package. These files must be saved and moved with the workflow to the redeployment environment. We can also see that as a consequence of noise reduction the amount of *Packages* was reduced from ten to one *Package*. This means that the other nine packages were common for both workflow executions and that Taverna uses them by default. The *libnss-mdns* package is the only specific package required by the analysed workflow.

Figure 8c depicts elements that were used by the calibration workflow, but are not used by the analysed workflow. We can see that they are only data files of the calibration workflow and the workflow itself. This confirms that we did not remove other key dependencies of the workflow, like Debian packages or services.

In the *Define validation metrics* step of the VFramework we generate validation requirements. The workflow steps exchange only *Plain Text* data hence for all of the sub-requirements we use the *String Equality* metric. There are only three outputs in which we use the *Euclidean Distance* metric instead, because they produce floating point numbers.

6.1.3. Redeployment environment

We redeploy the workflow into an existing Linux environment that is used to run other workflows. The original platform was *Ubuntu 12.04.5 LTS*, while the redeployment platform is *Linux Mint 17 Qiana*.

We re-execute and monitor with the PMF the workflow that uses the original WSDL web service. Then we compare its context model with the context model of the original execution and discover that, apart from the different operating system, also the installed Java version differs, that is, the original system used *oracle java 7*, while the redeployment system uses *open jdk 8*. Despite these discrepancies, the validation performed in the *Validate workflow* step of the VFramework confirms that the workflow re-execution is valid, that is, it produces the same results as the original workflow.

Knowing that the platform differences do not affect workflow repeatability, we test the impact of the web service mock-up on the workflow re-execution. For this reason we run a mock-up application on a machine that is within the same sub-network. The application uses the intercepted original requests and responses. To make the workflow connect to the mock-up, we edit the DNS configuration in the redeployment machine. Thus, we redirect the traffic to and from the *ws.biosemantics.org* host to the machine on which the mock-up is deployed. No changes in the workflow file itself are necessary.

Then we re-execute the workflow and monitor it with the PMF. The mock-up log shows that the workflow made six GET requests asking for the WSDL scheme of the web service. It also made six POST requests containing SOAP requests for data. There were no requests from the workflow for which the mock-up did not have a response.

We validate the workflow re-execution that used the mock-up and all requirements are fulfilled. Thus the mock-up is a valid strategy to be used for workflows that use web services to ensure repeatable conditions.

(a) Original context model.

(b) The *annotate workflow* dependencies.

(c) The calibration workflow dependencies, not used in the *annotate workflow*.

Figure 8: Noise reduction process for the *annotate workflow*.

Figure 9: Comparison of context models of the re-executed *annotate workflow* that used original WSDL web service and its mock-up.

Figure 10: The *rshell workflow*.

Last, but not least, we compare the context models of both re-executions to identify impact of the mock-up on the changes in the workflow context model. Figure 9 presents results of this comparison. We can see that only the IP address of the host providing the external service has changed. There were no other differences (We do not take into account the *Infrastructure Functions*, because they correspond to the operating system processes which order is highly non-deterministic).

6.2. Rshell workflow

We first present the use case description and then describe how we completed the steps of the VFramework in the original and the redeployment environment.

6.2.1. Use case description

Figure 10 presents the *rshell workflow*. It finds the overlap between two datasets that contain genomic information (e.g. gene id, chromosome name, gene start, gene end), and computes basic statistics. A Kolmogorov-Smirnov test is applied in order to test for differences between the p-value distribution of the gene list that overlaps with the epigenetic file and the gene list that does not overlap. The workflow returns rows of the first file that overlap with the second file.

6.2.2. Original environment

Similar to the other use cases, in the *Run static analysis* step of the VFramework we convert the workflow definition file into the core of the context model and use SPARQL queries to analyse the workflow. We identify that the workflow consists of five steps that are *Rshell services*. These services communicate with an external host to execute R scripts.

Figure 11 depicts an excerpt of the context model describing the external service realizing the *transform file to gen range Service* workflow step. We can see that the service is run on a localhost which means that the R server is

```

PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
PREFIX dio: <http://timbus.teco.edu/ontologies/DIO.owl#>

SELECT ?node ?host ?port ?script
WHERE {
    ?node a dio:Node .
    ?node dio:Port ?port .
    ?node dio:Host ?host .
    ?node dio:Script ?script .
    FILTER (regex(str(?script), "library\\(\\..*\\)"))
}

```

Listing 1: SPARQL query checking whether the R scripts load specific libraries.

```

Property assertions: External_Service
Object property assertions +
  realizes transform_files_to_gen_rangesService
Data property assertions +
  Host "localhost"
  Script "library(GenomicRanges)
  #transform each file in GRanges format

  #t1 <- GRanges(seqnames = genes[.gene_chr],
  #             ranges = IRanges(genes[.gene_start], genes[.gene_end] ,
  names = genes$entrezgene))

  print ("t1")

  t1 <- GRanges(seqnames = genes[.gene_chr], ranges =
  IRanges(genes[.gene_start], genes[.gene_end] , names = genes$entrezgene))

  print ("t2")

  t2 <- GRanges(seqnames = epigeneticfile[.inter_chr], ranges =
  IRanges(epigeneticfile[.inter_start], epigeneticfile[.inter_end]))

  print ("t1_t2_done")
  #t2 <- GRanges(seqnames = cpg$chrom,
  #             ranges = IRanges(cpg$chromStart, cpg$chromEnd))
  ..
  Port "6311"

```

Figure 11: Analysis of the static part of the context model.

started on the same machine in which the workflow executes. The workflow engine and the service communicate on port 6311. The context model also contains the R script that is executed at the given step in the R server.

The R scripts can require specific libraries to be installed in the R environment. In the analysed case, the script requires the *Genomic Ranges* library. Therefore, to re-execute the workflow, it is not sufficient to start the R server in parallel to the workflow engine, but also to load appropriate libraries. Using the SPARQL queries we can identify in the context model which steps require additional libraries. Listing 1 presents an example of a query that lists external services, their addresses, and ports that have scripts which require additional libraries.

Figure 12: Dependencies of the external R server.

We use this information to configure the redeployment environment in a proper way before the workflow is re-executed. We also consider creating a mock-up and for that purpose we capture and analyse the communication between the workflow engine and the R server. This is a *telnet* communication in which the scripts contained in the workflow are executed on the server. The server responds with standard messages confirming execution of consecutive scripts, but does not send back any data. Only the final result of running the sequence of scripts, that is the PNG image, is sent back by the server. Hence, we conclude that the service is stateful (depends on the sequence of previously executed commands) and requires more complex implementation than a lookup table used for the stateless web services (the response does not depend on the history of previous requests), like used in the other use cases. For this reason, the effort required to configure the R server that includes already identified libraries is lower than implementation of a mock-up of a stateful service.

Table 2: Mapping of requirements and metrics to their target values for the *rshell* workflow.

Requirement	Metric	Format	Target Value	Tolerance
R1.*	String Equality	Plain Text	0	0
R2.*	String Equality	Plain Text	0	0
R5.1	Image Fingerprint Equality Image Resolution Equality Absolute Error Count	PNG	0	0
R6.*	String Equality	Plain Text	0	0
R14	Execution Duration Ratio	N/A	1	30%

In the *Run dynamic analysis* step of the VFramework we run the PMF and create a dependency report. The workflow does neither shell calls nor does it require any specific Debian packages. It communicates with the 127.0.0.1 address which is the localhost. The report does not depict any dependencies of the R server, and especially none of the additional libraries needed by the R server, because the R server and its libraries are beyond the workflow's boundary.

However, it is also possible to detect dependencies of the server by monitoring the R server with the PMF. Figure 12 shows the dependencies of the R server that were detected by the PMF which attached to system process of the R server and monitored it for the period of time when the workflow was executing and exchanging data with the server. In the figure we can see that *Genomic Ranges* library, as identified by the static analysis of the workflow model, was loaded by the server. We can see that also other libraries like *IRanges* or *XVector* are used during the computation. PMF also detected 53 Debian packages and identified local paths of the files from which the scripts loaded data that was sent to the server. This shows that in settings when we have access to the environment of the external service and can monitor service execution, we are able to provide a modular documentation of both local and external dependencies.

In the *Define validation metrics* step of the VFramework we generate the validation requirements that we present in Appendix A. We depicted the requirements R3 and R4 in this list, but they did not get generated. This is because the workflow steps *read.files* and *transform.file_to_gen_ranges* do not have outputs. Hence, we are not able to validate them in the same way as we did it for the other workflows. If we look again at the script presented in Figure 11 we can observe the reason for that. The R scripts use their own variables to which they load data. These variables are persisted on the server and are available during the whole workflow execution. In this way the workflow steps exchange the data outside of the workflow engine! For this reason we are not able to validate these workflow steps automatically.

Table 2 depicts metrics that we generated for the identified requirements. Each sub-requirement of requirements R1, R2, and R6 is validated using *String Equality* metric. For the requirement R5.1 we use the *PNG Format Based Metrics*. The non-functional requirement R14 is validated in the same way as in the other use cases.

6.2.3. Redeployment environment

The original and the redeployment platforms are the same for this workflow as for the *annotate workflow* described in Section 6.1. In the redeployment platform we had to additionally install the R server and the *Genomic Ranges* library. We started the R server on port 6311 as identified in the *Run static analysis* step of the VFramework and then executed the workflow. We monitored its execution and compared it to the original context model. Based on this

Figure 13: The *ruby* workflow.

comparison we can observe that different Linux distribution is used, different java version is used (*openjdk8* instead of *java oracle 7*), an additional Debian package is loaded (*libatk*) and one is not loaded (*zlib1g*). Different Debian packages were loaded because the operating systems use different graphical user interfaces.

We validate the workflow and all requirements are fulfilled. Hence the above discrepancies did not have an impact on the workflow re-execution.

6.3. *Ruby workflow*

We first present the use case description and then describe how we completed the steps of the VFramework in the original and the redeployment environment.

6.3.1. *Use case description*

Figure 13 presents the *ruby workflow*. The workflow uses Ruby¹⁵ scripts to create *nanopublications*¹⁶ for a gene list that is associated to Huntington's disease as that was resulted from an experiment [46]. The nanopublications allow disseminating individual data as independent publications and can be uniquely identified and attributed to its author. They can be serialized to RDF.

6.3.2. *Original environment*

We run the static analysis of the workflow and identify one step that is a *Tool Invocation Service*. This step contains a command executing a Ruby script that is provided at the input of the workflow.

In the *Run dynamic analysis* step of the VFramework we monitor the workflow execution and create a dependency report that shows that:

- The workflow makes one shell call which uses */usr/bin/ruby*.
- This shell call requires additional files that are additional Ruby libraries, so-called gems, which are *rdf-1.1.17* and *slop-3.4.0*.
- The gems were installed for the version 1.9.1 of Ruby.
- The workflow has no external communications.

¹⁵<https://www.ruby-lang.org>

¹⁶<http://nanopub.org>

Figure 14: Comparison of context models of the original and the redeployed *ruby workflow*.

- The workflow requires one Debian package.
- The workflow creates *workdDir_I.nq.gz* file that is not part of the provenance traces.

The workflow owners explained that the *workdDir_I.nq.gz* file is the actual output of the workflow execution. It was produced during workflow execution by running the Ruby script. The file is not included in the Taverna provenance traces, because only the values exchanged between the workflow steps through their outputs and inputs are captured. Hence to validate workflows that perform tasks using shell calls we have two options:

1. Run the PMF in a mode that creates the context model only and manually select additional files that were detected by it.
2. Run the PMF in a mode that creates the context model and sources all identified files automatically.

In this experiment we choose the first option, that is, we ask the workflow owners to share the folder in which the workflow was executed that also includes the detected file. This corresponds to a practice used for creating Research Objects [22] that are not only used for sharing workflows but also input, output, and other data used in experiments.

6.3.3. Redeployment environment

We redeploy the workflow in a Linux environment that again differs in the version of the system. We move the workflow from the *Linux Mint 17 Qiana* to *Linux Ubuntu 15.04*. We install Ruby in version 1.9.1 and the required gems as described by the dependency report. Then we re-execute the workflow and monitor its execution with the PMF. We compare the context models of the re-executed and the original workflow. The results of the comparison are depicted in Figure 14.

We can see that the redeployment environment differs from the original:

- Different operating system is used.
- Eight new Debian packages are used.
- One Debian package is not used.

Figure 15: Comparison of context models of the re-execution missing dependencies and the correct re-execution.

- Different users ran the workflow.

These changes, similarly to the other use cases, can be attributed to the differences between the operating systems and exact versions of Java. To confirm these observations we validate the workflow in the next step.

Figure 16 presents the validation report created in the *Validate workflow* step of the VFramework. Only the execution duration requirement was fulfilled, while four other requirements failed:

- Requirements R1 and R3 failed because the output *output* was not identical. This was because the output *output* contains the standard output of the Ruby script invocation, which in turn contains timestamp and execution duration. Hence, these values are always different for every re-execution.
- Requirement R2 failed because the inputs specifying paths of the input parameters were not identical. The paths were different because different users were running the workflow in their home directories.
- Requirement R4 failed for the same reason as R1 and R3, because the output *output* was different. However, this requirement was measured differently than other two requirements, because not the provenance traces were used, but the actual file produced by the workflow that was detected by the PMF.

None of the requirements is violated due to the discrepancies between the environments. The requirements R2.3, R2.4, and R2.5 that failed have actually no impact on the validity of the workflow re-execution, because they require

Evaluation result: FAIL

There are 4 not fulfilled metrics. Please see tables below for details.

Comparison performed using following workflow execution traces

Original Workflow

ID: 1603d6f2-2171-4be4-bb6c-b3fa6f4e244f

Timestamp: 2015-11-30 15:44:13.433

Compared Workflow

ID: 340bb93c-b6b9-44e8-8305-1bc185ffa39

Timestamp: 2015-11-30 15:01:31.642

Table 1: Overview of requirements

Requirement	Description	Is Fulfilled
R1	The workflow step run_nanopub_ruby_script must have identical outputs	false
R2	The inputs of the workflow are the same	false
R3	The outputs of the workflow are the same	false
R4	The data files read and produced by the workflow must be identical.	false
R5	Execution duration of each of the workflow steps shall be similar	true

Table 2: List of requirements and metrics that failed.

Req	Sub-req	Sub-requirement description	Measurement point	Metric	Validity
R1	R1.2	The output output of workflow step run_nanopub_ruby_script must be identical.	output	String Equality	false
	R1.1	The output error of workflow step run_nanopub_ruby_script must be identical.	error	String Equality	true
R2	R2.5	The input ruby_script_path is identical.	ruby_script_path	String Equality	false
	R2.4	The input input_file_path is identical.	input_file_path	String Equality	false
	R2.3	The input output_file_path is identical.	output_file_path	String Equality	false
	R2.2	The input data_row_start_position is identical.	data_row_start_position	String Equality	true
	R2.1	The input entrezId_column_number is identical.	entrezId_column_number	String Equality	true
R3	R1.2	The output output of workflow step run_nanopub_ruby_script must be identical.	output	String Equality	false
	R1.1	The output error of workflow step run_nanopub_ruby_script must be identical.	error	String Equality	true
R4	R4.6	The file workDir_1.nq.gz is identical.	\$USERHOME/workDir_1.nq.gz	ZIP Format Metric	true

(a) Page 1/2

	R4.5	The file output is identical.	\$USERHOME/output/output	String Equality	false
	R4.4	The file poised_promoter_genes.txt is identical.	\$USERHOME/input/poised_promoter_genes.txt	String Equality	true
	R4.3	The file hdnanopubs.rb is identical.	\$USERHOME/input/hdnanopubs.rb	String Equality	true
	R4.2	The file converter.rb is identical.	\$USERHOME/input/converter.rb	String Equality	true
	R4.1	The file error is identical.	\$USERHOME/output/error	String Equality	true

(b) Page 2/2

Figure 16: Validation report for the ruby workflow.

identity of paths of the input files. The requirements R4.2, R4.3, and R4.4 are more important, because they validate the actual data used to run the workflow. They are fulfilled, which means that the data provided to the workflow is identical, but simply located in a different directory. Similarly, the real output of the workflow is the *workDir_1.nq.gz* file, the contents of which are identical.

The data files that were detected by the PMF and grouped under requirement R4 were validated also using the VPlanComparator. Hence we ran the file format characterization tool to identify their format and on that basis choose suitable metrics. In the given example, the *workDir_1.nq.gz* is a compressed library for which comparison of hashes shows discrepancies. This is due to a different header of the file. The actual data inside the library is the same and for this reason we used the *ZIP Format Metric* that aggregates results of metrics used to validate files contained within the library.

The requirements validating the data used by the workflow, as well as the data created by the workflow are fulfilled, hence we state that the workflow re-execution is replicable.

As we already observed in the evaluation, workflows that make shell calls depend on other software libraries and packages installed in the environment. Any of their dependencies missing can stop the workflow from executing and that is why the *Verify environment* step of the VFramework is dedicated to verification of workflow dependencies. We make one more experiment in which we evaluate how the VFramework detects workflow re-executions that fail to re-execute in a new environment and how it helps in identifying the cause of failure. For this reason, we modify the environment used in the previous redeployment by removing *gem* packages required by the *ruby workflow* to execute. We monitor the re-execution of the workflow with the PMF and then compare its context model with the context model of the previous valid re-execution.

The re-executed workflow produces errors which we observe in its error output. The error message informs that some libraries required by the workflow are missing and this information already explains the reason for the workflow execution to fail. However, the implementations of other workflows using shell calls can be different, for example, the standard error output of the script does not necessarily have to be linked to the workflow output, or the message may not be informative to the user, because of the wrong exception handling mechanism implemented by an external library used. For this reason the analysis of context models is a universal method for detecting missing dependencies.

Figure 15 depicts the elements that are missing from the environment and which were present in the original re-execution. We can see that the *slop* and *rdf* gems were uninstalled. Furthermore, we can see that the *workDir_1.nq.gz* file was not created and the *converter.rb* script was not even loaded. Hence we know that the workflow missed gems and the error occurred in the other script loaded by the workflow (the workflow shell call uses two Ruby scripts). The comparison of context models correctly identified the reason for the workflow execution to break.

7. Discussion

We applied the proposed VFramework on three Taverna workflows from biomedical research domain. The selected workflows used five different types of workflow steps in their implementations: tool service, Beanshell, Rshell service, WSDL web service, and XPath service. The tool services, Beanshell and Rshell scripts required additional dependencies to be present either in the local environment in which the workflows executed, or a specific configuration of services which were accessed to complete steps of the workflows. The selected workflows are representative for the majority of workflows published on myExperiment [12].

In the experiments we re-executed the workflows in environments differing in the version of the operating system (Linux Ubuntu 12 and 15), and its distribution (Linux Ubuntu and Mint). We thus showed in what way the VFrame-

work can be applied to identify the impact of software dependencies not only when workflows are re-executed in an exactly identical environment, but also in a similar environment.

The workflows analysed differ in a number of additional dependencies required to execute them. We showed that workflows that have fewer platform specific (local) dependencies, like the *annotate workflow*, can be almost automatically verified and validated regardless of the execution platform. This is because they do not depend on specific tools that must be present in the system and require only the workflow engine and external web services for their execution.

Although the changes, or especially unavailability, of the external web services are a serious threat to the replicability of experiments, we used a universal method of creating mock-ups for web services that can be used to replace the original web-services. Thus we reduced workflow dependability on external services and enabled replication of experiments that use the original data. Furthermore, we demonstrated that the proposed implementation does not require re-engineering of workflows and do not alter the workflow execution environment.

The other two use cases (the *rshell workflow*, and the *ruby workflow*) had more system specific dependencies and therefore more manual actions were required to re-execute, verify, and validate them. The *rshell workflow* used the R language to execute scripts using an R server that was accessed through a service. We performed the static analysis of the workflow model using SPARQL queries. Using this information we configured the Rshell server running in parallel to the workflow execution. We were not able to verify the server configuration using the dynamic workflow monitoring, because the server was not within the workflow boundaries. However, we were able to monitor in parallel the server to identify its dependencies that are loaded when workflow communicates with it.

Furthermore, in case of workflows heavily depending on shell calls to complete their steps, we recommend that the workflow owners make a test redeployment of their workflow into a clean machine before they publish their workflow. Thus they ensure that the information contained in the context model is sufficient for the redeployment. The current implementation of tools allows detecting all dependencies, but cannot identify ways in which these have to be installed. For this reason, explicit information from the workflow owner would make the porting process easier.

Using automatically generated validation requirements we were capable of detecting alterations on different stages of workflow processing and based on these we were able to identify steps in which workflow re-execution was altered. The application of format specific metrics enabled us to correctly compare the data collected for validation. For example, for the *ruby workflow* we compared two archives which contents were identical, while the hashes, which would be computed in a generic case, were different. This was because of a timestamp included in the header of the archive that must be ignored for proper validation.

The evaluation also confirmed that validation of workflow executions using only the provenance traces is not sufficient. This is because workflows using shell calls can read and write files without workflow engine mediation. Thus, these files are not included in the provenance traces. Such files are detected during workflow monitoring using the PMF. We demonstrated in the *ruby workflow*, that the actual inputs and outputs of the workflow contain only paths to the data provided to the workflow and information whether the workflow execution was correct, but do not contain the data. Validation of such data will fail for all re-executions, because the paths in which the data is located can be different, and the standard output also contains execution timestamps. For this reason, we focused on requirements that validated the files detected by the PMF as those which were accessed by the workflow during execution. Thus we validated the actual inputs and outputs of the workflow that have scientific value to the researcher.

Furthermore, not all of the Rshell services have outputs that can be validated. For such steps we cannot generate requirements. Such steps exchange data through global variables created in a remote service. These variables are

persisted on the server and are available during the workflow execution. In this way the workflow steps exchange the data outside of the workflow engine. Thus verification and validation of such workflows resembles black box testing techniques, in which only the inputs and outputs of the workflow can be validated, but not the intermediate steps.

Last, but not least, during the re-execution the *ruby workflow* we noticed that for some re-executions our criteria stating that all requirements must be identical to recognize the re-execution as repeatable were too strict. In these cases, use case experts could argue that violation of some of the metrics does not have real impact on the repeatability. For this reason, we suggest that the workflow owners generating the requirements in the original environment analyse which of these requirements and metrics are crucial for workflow replicability. Adjusting metric target values, adding comments, or removing unnecessary requirements will result in relaxing the conditions.

The general conclusion from the case study is that special attention must be paid to workflows with platform specific dependencies, because their analysis is more complex and requires more effort during verification as opposed to workflows with no dependencies, for which the framework can be almost fully automated. We are aware that removing the dependencies is not possible, due to the distributed nature of modern science, as well as the fact that well-established practices and tools already exist. However, workflow owners wanting to improve repeatability of their workflow executions should consider the guidelines listed below. The VFramework and tools described in this paper can be used to implement them.

- **Analyse dependencies and evade shell calls**

Some of the tasks performed by shell calls can be completed using Beanshells that are better portable and explicitly listed in the workflow definition file.

- **Write code that runs on all platforms**

If a shell call cannot be evaded, then provide its alternative invocation to be picked automatically depending on the execution environment.

- **Publish experiment setup and context**

Provide a list of tools which need to be present to make the workflow runnable. If you use Linux-based systems you can automatically collect them and store them in the context model. If your workflow uses additional tools that must be installed in the system, or services that are configured in a specific way describe how to configure the tools and provide specific settings you have used.

- **Publish validation data**

Provide evidence about the original execution, to which the re-execution can be compared to. Publish not only the provenance traces of the execution, but also other data files that were used and created by the workflow.

- **Specify validation requirements**

Describe which workflow requirements must be met to validate the workflow re-execution. You can choose from the list of automatically generated requirements.

- **Test the replicability on your own**

If your workflow has many complex dependencies, check whether the accompanying data you provide with the workflow is sufficient for its re-execution by doing one on a clean machine.

8. Conclusion

Complex and data driven experiments form the basis of biomedical research. Recent findings warn that the context in which the software is run, that is the infrastructure and the third party dependencies, can have a crucial impact on the final results delivered by a computational experiment. This implies that in order to replicate the same result, not only the same data must be used, but also it must be run on an equivalent software stack.

In this paper we presented the VFramework that enables assessing replicability of workflows. It identifies whether any differences in software dependencies among two executions of the same workflow exist and whether they have impact on the produced results. The VFramework uses the context model which is an extensible ontology allowing for description of workflow and its dependencies.

We also conducted a case study in which we investigated the impact of software dependencies on replicability of Taverna workflows used in biomedical research. We tested the impact of software dependencies not only by re-executing workflows in exact environments, but also in similar environments differing in operating system distribution and configuration. We investigated to what extent the impact of external services can be minimised by using service mock-ups. We also tested in what way automatic workflow execution capturing helps in identifying reasons for workflows to break.

The results show that the VFramework can be used to identify the impact of software dependencies on the replicability of scientific workflows. Furthermore, we observed that despite the fact that the case study focused on workflows executed in a controlled environment, the workflows had specific workflow dependencies requiring specific tools to be installed and configured in the environment. Such workflows are prone to have lower replicability than workflows consisting of standardised elements. Furthermore, we observed that tasks completed by these tools are not documented in provenance traces, thus making the provenance traces incomplete. Based on our findings we defined guidelines for workflow owners that enable them to improve replicability of their workflows.

Future work will focus on analysis of workflow engines architecture and identification of the best way of introducing proposed recommendations. We are also going to apply our framework on further use cases, potentially using different workflow engines.

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Appendix A. Automatically generated requirements for the *rshell* workflow

- R1** The workflow step *calculate_overlaps* must have identical outputs.
- R1.1** The output *non_overlapping_genes_pvals_out* of the workflow step *calculate_overlaps* must be identical.
 - R1.2** The output *overlapping_genes_pvals_out* of the workflow step *calculate_overlaps* must be identical.
- R2** The workflow step *ks.test* must have identical outputs.
- R2.1** The output *ks_p* of the workflow step *ks.test* must be identical.
 - R2.2** The output *ks_D* of the workflow step *ks.test* must be identical.
- R3** (The workflow step *spread_files* must have identical outputs.)
- This workflow step does not have outputs. This step cannot be validated.*
- R4** (The workflow step *transform_files_to_gen_ranges* must have identical outputs.)
- This workflow step does not have outputs. This step cannot be validated.*
- R5** The workflow step *ecdf_plot* must have identical outputs.
- R5.1** The output *cn* of the workflow step *ecdf_plot* must be identical.
- R6** The inputs of the workflow are the same.
- R6.1** The input *gene_end* is identical.
 - R6.2** The input *gene_start* is identical.
 - R6.3** The input *mapped_gene_file* is identical.
 - R6.4** The input *workingdir* is identical.
 - R6.5** The input *epigenomic_file* is identical.
 - R6.6** The input *genespvals* is identical.
 - R6.7** The input *epigenomic_file_chr* is identical.
 - R6.8** The input *epigenomic_file_end* is identical.
 - R6.9** The input *epigenomic_file_start* is identical.
- R7** The outputs of the workflow are the same.
- R2.1** The output *ks_p* of the workflow step *ks.test* must be identical.
 - R2.2** The output *ks_D* of the workflow step *ks.test* must be identical.
 - R5.1** The output *cn* of the workflow step *ecdf_plot* must be identical.
- R8** Execution duration of each of the workflow steps shall be similar.